

Diffuse leiomyomatosis uterus, rare case report with review of literature

Authors:

Ankita Girdhar, Neelam Sood

Senior Resident, Department of Pathology and Laboratory Medicine, Deen dayal upadhyay hospital (Govt of NCT), Hari nagar, New Delhi

Senior consultant, Department of Pathology and Laboratory Medicine, Deen dayal upadhyay hospital (Govt of NCT), Hari nagar, New Delhi

Corresponding Author:

Ankita Girdhar

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ABSTRACT:

Diffuse uterine leiomyomatosis (DLM), a rare benign myometrial disorder marked by uniform, diffuse proliferation of smooth muscle nodules throughout the uterus. Its clinical and imaging features often resemble multiple discrete uterine leiomyomas, leading to frequent preoperative misdiagnosis.¹ We present a case of 48 year old postmenopausal female (Para 2, living 2) with diffuse uterine leiomyomatosis (DLM). She presented with abnormal uterine bleeding. Ultrasound showed bulky uterus with large uterine fibroids. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the whole abdomen revealed an enlarged uterus with large intramural fibroid of size 10.7 × 8.7 × 8.5 cm in the right side fundus region and body of uterus displacing the endometrium towards left side along with numerous coalescing fibroids in rest of the myometrium. Total abdominal hysterectomy was performed. The specimen showed multiple coalescent nodules occupying almost entire myometrium. Multiple sections confirmed coalescent leiomyomata with merging boundaries with focal areas of hydropic change and myxoid degeneration. A diagnosis of diffuse uterine leiomyomatosis was signed out. This case is being presented for its rarity.

Keywords: DLM (diffuse uterine leiomyomatosis), myometrium, total abdominal hysterectomy, MRI

INTRODUCTION:

Leiomyomas are one of the most common benign entity among uterine neoplasms, commonly referred to as fibroids that present as well circumscribed masses within the myometrium radiologically.¹ In contrast to multiple leiomyomatosis, diffuse uterine leiomyomatosis (DLM) is a rare and poorly understood variant. It is characterised by the near complete replacement of the myometrium with numerous, confluent, poorly delineated smooth muscle nodules.² According to English literature so far < 50 cases have been reported.¹ Etiology of DLM is still not clear but may involve genetic factors. Main differential diagnosis to be considered are Hybrid leiomyomas, intravenous leiomyomatosis, diffuse uterine adenomyosis, endometrial stromal tumor and other hereditary syndromes.^{2,3,4} This manuscript illustrates radiological findings and histopathological findings of DLM. Rate of early diagnosis of diffuse uterine leiomyomatosis is rare as it is often misdiagnosed as common multiple uterine leiomyomas prior to

surgery.^{3,4} The management of DLM depends on the age as fertility sparing treatment with minimally invasive hysteroscopic removal of submucosal fibroids Or treatment with gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) agonists or uterine artery embolization (UAE), are increasingly being used worldwide.¹

CASE REPORT:

A 48 year old postmenopausal female (P2, L2) presented with abnormal uterine bleeding. Ultrasound showed bulky uterus with large uterine fibroid and multiple small leiomyomata. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the whole abdomen revealed an enlarged uterus with numerous coalescing fibroids in the myometrium largest being 10.7 × 8.7 × 8.5 cm. Post contrast study reveals heterogenous enhancement of fibroid but less than rest of the myometrium. Patient underwent total abdominal hysterectomy with a clinical diagnosis AUB-L.

Fig 1a,1b - Axial T2-weighted image showing a grossly enlarged uterus with multiple T2 heterogeneous signal intensity intramural fibroids in the lower uterine segment and extensively thickened myometrium in the fundal region and upper uterine segment

Gross examination showed Uterus with cervix measuring 13x12x7.5 cm with attached bilateral fallopian tubes and bilateral ovaries. Endometrial cavity was pushed towards one side on cut surface. Myometrial maximum thickness measuring 13 cm. Endometrial thickness was 1-2 mm. Myometrial surface show multiple coalescing and tiny nodules with imperceptible boundaries, occupying almost entire myometrium.

Fig2 a 2b - Cut Section show multiple coalescent, variable sized nodules of smooth muscle cells with uniform myometrial thickening

Microscopic examination showed numerous coalescing nodular leiomyomas found scattered in the myometrium the borders were merging with each other. The coalescent nodules were composed of plump spindle cells growing in an irregular fascicular and whorling pattern. The spindle cells had eosinophilic cytoplasm and cigar-shaped nuclei, infrequent mitosis and minimal anisonucleosis. There were intervening focal hydropic and myxoid degeneration along with focal collections of lymphocytes.

Fig 3a, 3b - Section showing multiple bundles of smooth muscles with intervening myxoid and lymphoid infiltrate (H &E, x 400) No necrosis was identified. No vascular invasion or intravascular pattern was identified. The myometrium was thinned out towards periphery (H &E, x 100).

Differential diagnoses considered were : Hybrid leiomyomas, intravenous leiomyomatosis, diffuse uterine adenomyosis, endometrial stromal tumor and were ruled out based on the morphology. The histological features were thus suggestive of Diffuse uterine leiomyomatosis.

DISCUSSION:

Diffuse uterine leiomyomatosis is a highly uncommon benign myometrial disorder defined by the extensive proliferation of smooth muscle cells throughout the uterus, resulting in a symmetrically enlarged uterus composed of innumerable, small, poorly demarcated nodules. Unlike typical leiomyomas, DLM lacks discrete encapsulated masses, often leading to diagnostic ambiguity both clinically and radiologically^{1,2}. According to English literature so far < 50 cases have been reported¹. Etiology of DLM is still not clear but may involve genetic factors². DLM usually affects female between third to fourth decade of life. ¹Patients usually present with abnormal uterine bleeding, chronic pelvic discomfort, or infertility, as in this case which presented with abnormal uterine bleeding as in this case.

Diagnostic utility of radiological investigations of this entity is higher for MRI as compared to Ultrasonography. Fibroids typically appear as well-defined, hypoechoic masses within the uterine wall, though their echogenicity can vary depending on the presence of degeneration, calcification, or cystic changes. Careful scanning in multiple planes is essential to ensure accurate characterization and to avoid overlooking smaller lesions⁵.

Histologically, DLM is characterized by widespread, benign smooth muscle proliferation in a fascicular pattern, devoid of cytologic atypia, coagulative necrosis, or elevated mitotic activity. Immunohistochemical staining typically shows diffuse positivity for smooth muscle markers (desmin, SMA) and hormonal receptors (ER, PR), consistent with leiomyomatous origin⁸. MRI shows markedly symmetrically enlarged uterus replaced by multiple nodules of low to intermediate intensity on T2W images. The nodules blend with each other¹.

However, due to the diffuse and subtle nature of the nodules, imaging findings can often be mistaken for other uterine pathologies, such as diffuse uterine adenomyosis, Hybrid leiomyomas, intravenous leiomyomatosis, endometrial stromal tumor and other hereditary syndromes.^{2,3,4} Endometrial stromal tumors (ESTs), particularly low-grade variants, can also simulate DLM due to their infiltrative behavior and potential for vascular invasion. On MRI, ESTs typically exhibit a heterogeneously hyperintense signal on T2-weighted imaging (T2WI), reflecting variable degrees of cystic, hemorrhagic, necrotic, and other degenerative components.⁶ Furthermore, ESTs may

present with infiltrative margins and myometrial permeation, unlike the well-demarcated yet unencapsulated pattern observed in DLM as in this case. However, these tumors generally consist of uniform small cells distinctly different from smooth muscle cells and commonly express CD10 immunoreactivity, a marker that is typically absent in DLM.³

Unlike adenomyosis, MRI features typically demonstrate ill-defined, low signal intensity areas on T2-weighted and T1 fat-suppressed sequences. These regions often contain small (2–7 mm) rounded cystic foci exhibiting high signal intensity due to hemorrhagic content.⁷ Adenomyosis show the presence of benign endometrial glands surrounded by endometrial stroma dispersed within hypertrophied myometrium where as DLM exhibits a uniform proliferation of smooth muscle bundles that entirely replace the myometrium without glandular elements. The absence of endometrial-type components remains critical in excluding adenomyosis. Because of the overlapping features, they may pose a diagnostic challenge, and histologic confirmation is often required.^{2,3,4} IHC marker for adenomyomas are desmin and caldesmon, smooth muscle actin, histone deacetylase 8, smooth muscle myosin heavy chain, oxytocin receptor ER, PR and WT1.⁸

Unlike diffuse uterine leiomyomatosis, hybrid leiomyomas, a term coined by FIGO location based subclassification of leiomyomas are typically discrete masses with heterogeneous morphology. Hybrid leiomyomas may demonstrate heterogeneous signal intensity on MRI due to their mixed histologic components. Hybrid leiomyomas (also known as mixed-type leiomyomas) are composed of variable combinations of features seen in conventional, cellular, myxoid, or atypical leiomyomas⁴.

IVL exhibits intraluminal extension, occasionally with a serpiginous pattern, which may mimic a malignant process or even suggest metastatic disease on imaging. Definitive categorization is possible through characteristic histological findings. When distinguishing DLM from intravascular leiomyomatosis (IVL), the presence of tumor growth within venous or lymphatic channels is a defining feature of IVL, which was ruled out in this case. On MRI, intravenous leiomyomatosis (IVL) typically presents as serpentine or worm-like structures, showing isointense signal on T1-weighted images and heterogeneous signal on T2-weighted images, with areas of high signal intensity evident on diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI).⁹

Thus, a combined evaluation of morphological features and immunohistochemical profile is essential to distinguish DLM from these mimickers and avoid

misclassification, especially in cases with extensive or atypical presentation.

The pathophysiology of DLM remains incompletely elucidated, though its estrogen- and progesterone-dependent growth pattern has been postulated based on its reproductive-age predominance and clinical regression post-menopause or oophorectomy¹⁰.

Clonality analysis has provided insight into the biological behavior of DLM. A study by Baschinsky et al. demonstrated monoclonal origins of the multiple nodules, suggesting that despite their widespread appearance, the lesions may arise from a single progenitor cell line, consistent with the pathobiology of more typical uterine leiomyomas¹¹. Molecularly, leiomyoma development is strongly influenced by estrogen and progesterone, and is associated with various genetic alterations. According to Commandeur et al., mutations in MED12, rearrangements in HMGA2, and activation of signaling pathways such as TGF- β , Wnt, and PI3K/AKT/mTOR contribute to the proliferative behavior of smooth muscle cells in the uterus¹². These insights suggest potential therapeutic targets and also help contextualize the disease in a broader genetic and syndromic framework.

DLM, although rare, may manifest within the context of certain inherited syndromes:

- ◆ **Reed syndrome** (Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Carcinoma), caused by mutations in the fumarate hydratase (FH) gene, is most frequently associated with multiple uterine and cutaneous leiomyomas. Although DUL is not a hallmark of this syndrome, its presentation may overlap, particularly in younger patients with extensive uterine involvement^{12,13}.
- ◆ **Cowden syndrome**, a disorder linked to PTEN gene mutations, includes a spectrum of benign and malignant growths. Uterine leiomyomas have been reported, and while DUL specifically is rare, its presence should prompt evaluation for Cowden syndrome if other systemic features are present¹².
- ◆ **Proteus syndrome**, resulting from mosaic AKT1 mutations, is characterized by progressive, asymmetric overgrowth of multiple tissues, including connective and smooth muscle components. This hyperactivation of the PI3K/AKT pathway may contribute to smooth muscle hyperplasia within the uterus¹².
- ◆ **Alport syndrome**, a hereditary nephropathy associated with COL4A3, COL4A4, or COL4A5 gene mutations, has been rarely associated with uterine leiomyomas. Although the exact mechanism remains unclear, disruptions in basement membrane structure may create an environment conducive to abnormal smooth muscle proliferation.¹²

These syndromic associations are particularly important when evaluating patients with early-onset, recurrent, or unusually extensive uterine smooth muscle tumors. A detailed family history and dermatological or renal assessment may help identify patients who would benefit from genetic counseling and testing. DLM represents a distinctive entity within the spectrum of uterine smooth muscle proliferations. Its diagnosis requires an integrated approach combining clinical evaluation, imaging, pathology, and when indicated genetic assessment. Though management remains challenging due to the diffuse pattern of involvement, emerging minimally invasive techniques offer hope for improved outcomes in select cases. Awareness of potential syndromic associations, including Reed syndrome, Cowden syndrome, Proteus syndrome, and Alport syndrome, is essential for holistic care and long-term surveillance.^{12,13}

From a therapeutic standpoint, treatment options for DLM remain limited. Traditional myomectomy is often not feasible due to the diffuse infiltration and absence of distinct nodules. Total hysterectomy has historically been the mainstay of definitive management². However, novel minimally invasive techniques such as hysteroscopic removal using thoracic forceps in a no-distension environment have been introduced to address localized lesions in women seeking fertility preservation¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

Diffuse uterine leiomyomatosis is an uncommon and often misdiagnosed condition with significant implications for fertility and surgical management. Clinicians should maintain a high index of suspicion in patients presenting with a diffusely enlarged uterus and nonspecific imaging findings. Early and accurate diagnosis is essential for optimal treatment planning. Clonal analysis undertaken if economically feasible.

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